

TECHNOLOGICAL PROGRESS: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich,
Valiev Lochin Azamatovich,
Yusupov Shermatilla Rahmatovich,
Abdukarimova Gulchehra Baratovna,
Tashkenbayev Tashtemir Tashkenbayevich
(<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0071-5730>)

Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Tashkent State Transport University 1,
Temiryolchilar Str., Tashkent, 100167, Uzbekistan (sariosiyo73@mail.ru)
(ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8252-6396>)

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Tashkent State Transport University 1,
Temiryolchilar Str., Tashkent, 100167, Uzbekistan e-mail: (valiyev133@gmail.com)
(<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3684-0066>)

Tashkent State Transport University 1, Temiryolchilar
Str., Tashkent, 100167, Uzbekistan (shermatillayusupov56@gmail.com)
(<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4748-958X>)

Tashkent State Transport University 1, Temiryolchilar Str.,
Tashkent, 100167, Uzbekistan (baratovnagulchehra@gmail.com)
(<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8383-0522>)

Tashkent State Transport University 1, Temiryolchilar Str., Tashkent, 100167,
Uzbekistan (tashtemir6026@gmail.com)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13382929>

Abstract: The article analyzes the positive and negative aspects of technology for human and social life. It is studied that technology and humanity are interrelated like the unity of opposites in philosophy and the law of struggle. Also, the concepts of techno-optimism and techno-pessimism were scientifically and philosophically evaluated and necessary conclusions were drawn.

Keywords: Man, technology, society, development, techno-optimism, techno-pessimism..

1. INTRODUCTION

Good and bad are in human nature. However, we do not want to conclude with this opinion that when babies come into the world, they can do evil as well as good. We only want to say that every child who comes into the world, as he grows up as a human being, has tendencies to do both good and evil. Over time, the environment in the society in which he lives has an impact on the formation of these tendencies in a person from one side or another. Industrial, scientific and technical progress, which is a product of human intelligence, is also considered to have such an effect. If we look at the works of thinkers, we can see the

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In fact, the technical process has now become an integral part of any human activity and society as a whole. [Salimov, Allamurodov, Toshkhojaev 2023: 342]. However, there is another side to the issue, that is, in the humanistic environment, the critical attitude towards technical development in modern society increases, and attention is primarily paid to its negative aspects. Whether the technique is necessary or not, or whether the technique has a positive

or negative value. These two views have become the main theme of the philosophy of technology. [Salimov, 2022: 110]. The concepts of two main features of technology - technooptimism and technopessimism - occupy an important place in the stages of development in the philosophy of technology. In fact, "in the framework of social relations, industry has a double influence on the life of a person and society, that is, it has negative and positive aspects. In the language of science, techno-optimism - technology development serves to improve human life, while techno-pessimism - technology development has a negative effect on humanity. [Salimov, Savriddinov 2023: 340]. It is related to the application of logical-epistemological analysis of technology, that is, its conceptual development, which is one of the main problems of the philosophy of technology.

3. ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

There are various philosophical concepts of technology, one of them is the rational-technical concept, which is characteristic of the culture of the new era. Its main principles are described in the works of F.

Bacon, T. Hobbs, R. Descartes, B. Pascal. The concept of E. Kapp regarding the evolution of technology is known and famous. This concept was described in E. Kapp's work "The main directions of the philosophy of technology". M. Heidegger was the first to scientifically base the ontology of technology and, emphasizing the ontological nature of technology, declares that the main principle of technology as an object is the way of humanity's self-realization. A number of philosophers such as F. Rapp, G. Ropol, K. Mitcham studied the problems of the philosophy of technology and its history. In particular, F. Rapp distinguishes the following several stages describing the history of the philosophy of technology: 1) from an anthropological point of view, man is considered in his natural, biological state, with the needs arising from him (K. Marks, E. Kapp, I. Gerdner, A. Gelen), and technical inventions are interpreted as a continuation of human organs, interpreted as a new means of continuing evolution.

4. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

All types of technology, namely manufacturing industry, transport industry, heavy industry, light industry, mining industry, metallurgical industry, etc. are also harmful to human society in some way. Today's rapid development of technology, we know what disasters follow in its wake. First of all, the air we breathe has already lost its purity. We cannot call the water we drink as clear and clean as before. The contents of the delicacies we eat are also full of substances that are harmful to our health. After all, the toxic gases, life-threatening liquid and various solid wastes produced by the industry are not disappearing anywhere. They become part of the air we breathe, become clouds, and fall on us in the form of rain and snow. The waste is mixed with the soil and absorbed into the composition of our drinking water. And various agricultural products grown from them are the beauty of our table. As a result, new diseases appear and many people are dying. We also know very well the consequences of accidents in large-scale industrial facilities, in particular, in nuclear power plants. It is difficult to enumerate the number of unpleasant traffic accidents and the number of people injured as a result of them. Or let's take the case of weapons, one of the industrial products. Millions of people died in the next century due to the use of these weapons. Even now, many people are being killed in conflicts that are happening in different parts of the world and even in countries that are recognized as peaceful. Unfortunately, these weapons are likely to kill many more people in the future. The saddest thing is that humanity has in its hands terrible weapons capable of repeatedly destroying

the earth. As if this was not enough, they are trying to improve it further. However, thinking about the need to stop such a manifestation of progress is not absurd, empty nonsense. Because it has reached its last level, from which it is impossible to go further. Although there is no limit to such progress, humanity does not understand it and says to itself: Stop, stop! He does not say that there is no way out of this." However, instead of coming to their senses, humanity is trying to cover up their actions with various excuses. Apparently, they were forced to create ultra-modern weapons to protect themselves. When asked who, they say the name of the competing countries. For example, by arming the USA, it showed defense against the aggression of the former USSR. Now Russia and China pose a threat to the USA. India points to Pakistan as a source of danger, and Pakistan points to India, and the list goes on and on. But the end of this situation does not lead to good. Metaphorically speaking, this behavior of mankind can be compared to a person sawing a branch of a tree on which he is sitting. One is afraid to think about what terrible consequences it will lead to if the very modern nuclear, chemical, bacteriological and other types of weapons in the hands of the powerful countries of the world are put into action. One thing is certain, there will be no winning side in a war where such weapons are used. Maybe everyone will be defeated, both those who participated in the war and those who did not. The earth will be turned into a mound, social relations will be destroyed, progress will be pushed back several tens of thousands of years, and mankind will be condemned to start his life again from the primitive community system. If humanity can come out of this war safely.

Humanity must strive to change the path of technological development in a more favorable direction. Because technology development has both positive and negative aspects. Technology has entered our lives and we are used to it. Like it or not, technology has become an integral part of human life. Because, among our contemporaries who are living with us now, there are probably those who do not use industrial products, if we say in a language that you and I understand, technical achievements. For example, everyone has electricity in their homes, we all use our own vehicles or public transportation, every home has a television, a wired or wireless phone, most people have a computer, most people use refrigerators, washing machines, and air conditioners, and the list goes on. can be continued for a long time. This list proves that industrial products, technical samples, as an integral part of our daily life, have already become the essence of human life. To tell the truth, humanity cannot live without them and will not get used to it anymore. As

stated above, industry is needed by all people regardless of caste or class. And this industry or technique serves to form a mutually beneficial and reliable relationship between different categories of people. The most important thing is that industry is becoming more and more important in making people's lives easier year by year, improving their supply of material goods, and creating a prosperous way of life. Many more convincing arguments and logically proven opinions can be given about the positive role of industry and technology in human life and its incomparable importance in the development of human society. However, at this point, the respected reader has a valid question. A few years ago, very dire conclusions were drawn about the dangers of industry to mankind, and now industry is rising into the blue. Which statement is correct, is the industry harmful or beneficial?

We will try to answer this question based on the conclusion that "industry is the cause of great problems and industry is also the source of countless benefits for the development of society." According to our conclusion, there are both negative and positive aspects of industry in human and social life. So to speak, we can say that the industry is both a friend and an enemy of mankind. If we continue our thought based on philosophical laws, humanity and industry develop in a dialectical relationship based on the law of unity and struggle of opposites. This dialectical relationship is beneficial to humanity on the one hand and harmful on the other. Humanity can no longer live without industry, but at the same time, it cannot accept some aspects of industrial development. The reason they cannot accept is that certain aspects of industrial development are having a destructive effect on humanity, or in other words, are leading humanity towards disaster. We have discussed these harmful effects in detail above. To explain more simply, industry and science and technology are developing against nature and life.

The laws of industrial, scientific and technical development contradict the laws of existence and development of nature, biosphere. Unfortunately, this conflict did not appear today or yesterday. The root of this conflict was in the early days of industry. However, this difference was not so noticeable in those days. As the years and centuries passed, this conflict became stronger and stronger and reached the current dangerous situation. The whole of humanity, including us as a part of it, is confused by the current complex situation. What to do? The question is difficult. It is difficult to answer. On one side there is development and growth, on the other side there is nature and the fate of life. It is impossible to stop the development of industry, science and technology so that it does not harm nature and

living things. Because humanity has learned to live on the basis of industrial, scientific and technical achievements. They made the way of life of mankind much more convenient, easier, modernized, etc. Now, humanity cannot abandon these conditions created for itself. Even if he says he will give up, there is no possibility or possibility. After all, the conditions for the existence of the current countries depend on the development of the entire industry and science and technology. Economic indicators of countries, socio-political situation, military-defense potential, household lifestyle of the population, cultural-educational level of life and processes in other areas are directly determined by industrial and scientific-technical development. To abandon industry and science and technology is to abandon the current civilization. It means exchanging the way of life we live now, all the comforts and opportunities - for the backward life of the middle ages.

As can be seen from the above considerations, the development of industry and science and technology cannot be stopped, it must continue to develop. This way also does not satisfy humanity. Because then the damage to nature and biosphere will continue. The current state of industrial and scientific-technical development is making the planet earth, the abode of life, uninhabitable. Otherwise, the loss of control over the nuclear and thermonuclear means at the disposal of humanity is likely to accelerate the occurrence of unprecedented ecological disasters on earth. As you can see, the development of Industry and science and technology cannot be stopped or continue in this way. Humanity is now in such a situation that, as the proverb says, if you cover your legs with a blanket, your head will not be covered, if you pull the blanket over your head, your legs will be exposed. The situation is similar now. So is it possible to get out of this situation? We think it is possible. From our point of view, the progress of industrial and scientific-technical development in its current form is unacceptable. Or to put it another way. It is necessary to revise the laws of industrial and scientific-technical development, which contradict the laws of existence and development of nature and biosphere. After all, we did not create nature, it and its laws of existence and development existed before us, independently of us. Therefore, we cannot change the laws of existence and development of nature. However, industry and science and technology are the product of human thinking, mental and physical activity. Therefore, it is possible to change the laws of industrial and scientific-technical development, to direct it in a direction acceptable to mankind. In particular, there are opportunities to adapt industrial and scientific-technical development to the laws of existence and development

of nature and the biosphere. It can be said that humanity has already started research on this path and is achieving certain results. For example, the transition of train locomotives from diesel fuel to electric power and the replacement of cars with internal combustion engines that run on gasoline, diesel and gas fuels such as propane and methane are replaced by electric cars. We know that electric cars run on electricity, even solar energy, and do not harm the environment.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, some aspects of industrial, scientific and technical progress in the current form are unacceptable for nature, biosphere and the future of humanity. The task that must be solved in a short period of time before humanity is to adapt and harmonize the laws of industrial and technical development with the laws of nature and the biosphere. Humanity should discover such ways of industrial and technical development that these ways should serve humanity not for its suffering, but for its future. The task now is the problem of various industrial enterprises, plants and factories that pollute the environment to a high degree. In the future, it is desirable to transfer all other branches of industry to alternative, environmentally friendly sources of energy. Otherwise, it is necessary to fundamentally change the principle of work in all areas of industry and create such high technologies that they do not have a destructive effect on the environment. Of course, creating a new way of working, discovering environmentally safe technologies cannot be realized by itself. For this, leaders, scientists, constructors, scientific researchers and specialists in that field are required to show their inquisitiveness, creativity, innovation, initiative. In general, this issue affects not only the social strata that we have listed above, but also people belonging to all categories and classes living in society..

REFERENCES

[1] Salimov, B.L. (2023). Negative consequences of science and technology development. International Conference Law, Economics and Tourism sciences in the modern world. 5(1), p. 5-10.
 [2] Salimov B.L. (2022). Ijtimoiy munosabatlarning kommunikatsiya va transport tizimi bilan deterministik bog'liqligining gnoseologik tahlili. Falsafa fanlari doktori dissertatsiyasi. O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti. Toshkent. 224 b.
 [3] Salimov, B., Madalimov, T. (2023). Transport falsafasi. [Globe Edit](#).

[4] Salimov. B.L., Abdimurodov, N.Sh., Savridinov, S.S. (2023). The Development of Automotive and Road Engineering Industries in a Deterministic Relationship. (2023). WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2(2), Page 338-341.
 [5] Salimov, B.L., Abdullaev, U.K., Makhkamov, M.R. (2023). The Development of the Automotive Industry and Road Construction are Interdependent. International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD). 1(2), Page 330-332.
 [6] Salimov, B.L., Allamurodov, K.B., Toshkhojaev, K.K. (2023). Prospects of Development of Communication and Transport System in Uzbekistan. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2(2), Page 342-346.
 [7] Salimov, B.L., Narzullaev, J.A., Sodikov, T.I. (2023). The Social Significance of Roads and Ongoing Road Construction Work. International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD). 1(2), Page 311-313.
 [8] Salimov, B.L. (2024). The social and philosophical importance of engineering thinking in engineering personnel training. Международная научно-практическая конференция «Устойчивое развитие транспорта: экономика, трансформация, логистика, ESG повестка». p. 100-112.
 [9] Salimov, B.L. (2023). The Importance of Sea Transport in the Communication System. Web of synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2(1), p. 272-275.
 [10] Salimov, B.L. (2023). The Influence of the Transport and Communication System on Social Relations. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Ie Education. 2(2), p. 209-212.
 [21] Юсупов, Шерматилла Рахматович. «ПРИОРИТЕТНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ НЕПРАВИТЕЛЬСТВЕННОГО СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА В ОЗДОРОВЛЕНИИ ДУХОВНОЙ СРЕДЫ». *Теоретическая и прикладная наука* 2 (2020): 743-748.
 [12] Ташкенбаева, Д. А. (2018). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ КРАЕВЕДЕНИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ ВОСПИТАНИЯ ГАРМОНИЧНО РАЗВИТОЙ ЛИЧНОСТИ. In *Колтинские чтения по краеведению и туризму* (pp. 119-121).
 [13] Salimov, B.L. (2023). Reforms in the Fields of Communication and Transport and their Social Impact. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Ie Education. 2(2), p. 227-230.
 [14] Salimov, B.L., Odilov, N.O., Odilov Sh.K. (2023). [The Social Importance of Roads and the Great Creative Works Being Carried Out in the Field of Road](#)

Construction in Uzbekistan. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Education. 2(2), p. 205-208.

[15] Salimov, B.L. (2021). The philosophical role of dialectical categories in human life. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. 1(6), p. 406-410.

[16] Salimov, B.L., Tursunov, Sh.R., Haydarov M.N. (2023). Synergetic approach in the analysis of social relations. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. 3(3), p. 1001-1007.

[17] Salimov, B.L., Tursunboeva, D.N. (2023). Development of communication and transport in Uzbekistan. International scientific and practical conference "The time of scientific progress". 2(9), p. 5-11.

[18] Salimov, B.L., Sharipov, Q.E. (2023). The role of social and moral values in the country's development. Innovative Technologies in Construction Scientific Journal. 1(1), p. 229-235.

[19] Baratov, R., Nuriddinov, S., Tokhtaboev, E., Achilova, G. "One Belt - One Road" Initiative - as a Modern Transport Logistics 2022AIP Conference Proceedings 2432,030058 <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0089703>

[20] Ramatov, J., Baratov, R., Jurabayev, N., Umarova, R., Mamajanova, G. Evolution of Railway Construction Development in Uzbekistan: Past and Prospects 2022AIP Conference Proceedings 2432,030011 <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0090845>

[21] Ramatov, J., Aleksandr, L., Baratov, R., Umarova, R., Djurabayev, N. Methodological principles for improving the scientific thinking of specialists (In the case of the transport system)(2024).<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0>

85188445036&doi=10.1063%2f5.0197376&partnerID=40&md5=4474bc5af94998337dd18f30da55ea5c

[22] Ramatov, J., Baratov, R., Jurabayev, N., Umarova, R., Mamajanova, G. 57767291700; 57768752000; 57768752100; 57768501200; 57767327400; Evolution of Railway Construction Development in Uzbekistan: Past and Prospects, (2022)

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85133024672&doi=10.1063%2f5.0090845&partnerID=40&md5=97754046d6658aa51f8ab1abade4b424>

[23] Jumaniyaz Ramatov, Rozigul Umarova, Guncha Mamajanova, and Nasiba Jumaniyazova. (2023). The origin and development history of the great silk road in Central Asia. Problems in the Textile and Light Industry in the Context of Integration of Science and Industry and Ways to Solve Them. Volume 3045 B p. 060006-1 – 060006-7.

[1] [22] Baratov, R. (2021). Prospects of Higher Education4System (on the Example of Uzbekistan). International Journal on Orange Technologies, 3(3), 128-131